

CARBON NANOTUBE-BASED SENSING OF MATRIX CRACKING IN CROSS-PLY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The pioneering research of Professor Anthony Kelly and co-workers in the 1970s studying the formation of matrix damage in laminated composites was a significant advance in the damage mechanics of composite materials. Recently, carbon nanotubes have been utilized to detect the onset and accumulation of cracks in composite laminates and sheds new light on this classical problem of transverse matrix cracking.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotubes, Matrix Cracking, Damage Mechanics

ABSTRACT

In a landmark paper published in 1971, Aveston, Copper and Kelly [1] first examined the multiple fracture of matrix in brittle matrix composites at high fiber volume fraction, as a result of applied tensile loads or thermal stresses induced by cooling from the stress-free temperature. An energy approach was utilized for analyzing the formation of a single matrix crack normal to the fiber in a unidirectional composite. Their elegant solution concludes that the composite strain at the formation of transverse matrix crack can be enhanced by suitable control of the elastic moduli of the fiber and matrix, fiber volume fraction and diameter, matrix surface energy, and the fiber-matrix interfacial strength. The pioneering research of Kelly and co-workers [2-4] (Aveston and Kelly, 1973; Kelly 1976; Aveston and Kelly, 1980) motivated tremendous interest in the composites community in general and at University of Surrey in particular.

The research conducted on the transverse cracking of cross-ply composites at the University of Surrey in the late 70s and early 80s signifies a period of tremendous intellectual excitement as well as the elegance of fundamental research with significant engineering relevance. Some of the key contributors were Bailey, Bader, Garrett, Parvizi, Curtis and Manders, just naming a few. Besides careful experimental observations they performed analytical modeling, using Aveston and Kelly's shear-leg approach, and interpreted the transverse cracking phenomenon by the concept of constrained cracking. It was a very enlightening experience that one of the present authors (T. W. Chou) had the privilege in witnessing some of the research activities in 1976 at Surrey.

For nearly four decades since the publication of the paper by Aveston, Cooper and Kelly, the matrix cracking problem has been studied by researchers using a broad array of experimental and analytical tools. However, with the advent of the science and technology of carbon nanotubes, there are the new capabilities in experiment and analysis to shed light on the classical problem of transverse matrix cracking.

In our research we have established that it is possible to form electrically percolating networks of carbon nanotubes throughout the polymer matrix in a fiber composite. Carbon nanotubes, which are three orders of magnitude smaller than traditional fiber reinforcement, are able to penetrate the matrix-rich regions among the fibers and between the layers of the composite and are minimally invasive to the structure of the composite. The nanotubes then become a distributed sensing network that can be utilized for sensing of both deformation and damage *in situ*. The technique is remarkably sensitive to the onset of matrix cracking and also holds the capability to distinguish between the types of damage [5-7]. This report focuses on experimental and theoretical research results aimed at establishing an approach for quantifying the microstructural evolution of damage with carbon nanotube networks.

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